

Digitalization Of “Pt Abc's Financial Operation

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ABSTRACT

Digitalization of financial information systems is a crucial aspect in improving the accuracy, efficiency, and transparency of financial data management within a company. Integration of technology in financial recording allows for process automation, but its implementation still faces various challenges. This study uses a qualitative descriptive method with a case study approach to analyze the recording of income and receivables and identify obstacles in implementing a digital system. The results of the study indicate that although the company has implemented a financial information system, there are still obstacles such as late customer payments and records that have not been fully digitized. Therefore, optimization of technology in the financial information system is recommended to improve efficiency and transparency in managing income and receivables.

Keywords: Digitalization, Financial Information System, Financial Recording, Efficiency

INTRODUCTION

Technological developments have driven digitalization in various sectors, including the financial industry. Digitalization in the financial aspect can increase efficiency in managing and recording financial transactions through the use of software and financial information systems. With sophisticated technology, companies can prepare financial reports accurately and on time and analyze financial data in more depth to support better decision making (Avira et al., 2023). Innovation in digital payment and transaction systems is accelerating the shift from conventional methods to technology-based services. This trend can be seen from the significant increase in digital transactions in Indonesia.

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Figure 1

Digital Economic and Financial Transaction Facts in Indonesia January 2022

Source: Department of Communication (2022)

In January 2022, digital economic and financial transactions in Indonesia experienced significant growth as shown in Figure 1. The value of electronic money transactions increased by 66.65% compared to the previous year, reaching IDR 34.6 trillion. Digital banking transactions also increased by 62.82%, with total transactions reaching IDR 4,314.3 trillion. Meanwhile, transactions using ATM cards, debit cards, and credit cards experienced a growth of 14.39%, with transaction values reaching IDR 711.2 trillion. The use of QRIS also experienced a sharp increase, with transaction amounts increasing by 290% and transaction volumes increasing by 326%. In response to this growth, Bank Indonesia increased the QRIS transaction limit from IDR 5 million to IDR 10 million per transaction, which came into effect on March 1, 2022 (Ministry of Communication, 2022). This development reflects the increasingly widespread adoption of digital technology in the Indonesian financial system.

Figure 2
 Digital Economy in Indonesia
 Source: Pratama (2021)

In Figure 2, the total growth of digital economic transactions in Indonesia has increased rapidly. In 2019, total digital transactions were recorded at US\$ 40.9 billion, then increased to US\$ 47 billion in 2020, and increased again to US\$ 70 billion in 2021. Projections for 2025 show a significant spike to US\$ 146 billion. This trend reflects the rapid development of the digital economy in Indonesia, driven by increasing adoption of technology and the use of digital transactions (Pratama, 2021). This trend of growing digital transactions not only reflects changes in consumer behavior but also highlights the importance of digitalization in various aspects of business, including financial information systems. In line with the findings of Avira et al. (2023), companies can improve operational efficiency, optimize financial resources, and make faster and more accurate decisions through automation of financial processes, real-time access to financial data, and the use of sophisticated analytical tools. However, even though the benefits of digitalization have been proven, there are still companies that still rely on manual systems in their operations. One of them is PT ABC, a distributor of household

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and decoration products, which until now still relies on manual recording in various aspects of its finances, including recording outgoing goods, issuing notes, billing, payroll, and tax recapitulation.

Therefore, digital transformation is an urgent need for PT ABC in improving operational efficiency and data accuracy. In the implementation process, the company needs to consider systematic stages, starting from mapping needs to evaluating the effectiveness of the implemented system. In addition, there is a gap in research on how the digitalization process can be optimally implemented in companies with manual recording systems that have been running for years. This article aims to analyze the challenges and impacts of digital transformation in PT ABC's operations. The focus of the research includes problems caused by the manual system as well as the potential for increasing efficiency in financial recording, tax management, and data analysis. The results of this study are expected to provide recommendations for optimal digitalization implementation strategies to improve the company's competitiveness and become a reference for other companies facing similar challenges.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Financial Information System

An information system is an integrated unit consisting of humans, computers, information technology, and work procedures, where these components work together to process data into information that supports decision-making, improves operational efficiency, and achieves organizational goals effectively (Rohman & Pratama, 2022). One type of information system that is important in the business world is a financial information system. According to Saputra et al. (2022), a financial information system is a system designed to manage, process, and present financial data to support the decision-making process in an organization. This system integrates various elements, including transaction recording, financial reporting, and data analysis that play a role in providing information for internal and external stakeholders. In its operation, the financial information system is based on three main principles, namely:

1. Fast, ensuring that accounting data is presented on time as needed.
2. Safe, emphasizing the importance of internal control to safeguard company assets.
3. Cheap, aims to reduce operational costs without reducing service quality.

The financial information system functions to increase transparency and accountability. This system works in real-time and automatically, so it can reduce errors and manipulation, support accurate strategic decision-making, and reduce operational costs. Accountability in cost management ensures that expenses are managed effectively for optimal results without waste (Nurani et al., 2025). In its implementation, according to Rohman & Pratama (2022), the financial information system utilizes information technology to increase the efficiency of transaction recording, reduce the risk of human error, and support the preparation of more systematic and accurate financial reports. Financial information systems have an important role in improving fiscal transparency, efficiency, and accountability. The main components of financial information systems (Aminuddin et al., 2024):

1. Hardware

Hardware includes physical equipment such as computers, printers, and UPS that support information processing and must meet standards to support the success of a financial information system.

2. Software

Includes a collection of programs used to run a computer.

3. Database

Includes a structured data collection used to store and manage financial information efficiently and allows multi-user access.

4. Procedures

Includes a series of rules and procedures used to ensure that financial information system processing runs consistently and according to standards.

5. Humans (brainware)

Including human resources involved in the management of information systems, they have a crucial role in the operation, analysis, and distribution of financial information produced by the system.

In its development, the financial information system is no longer only based on conventional recording but has transformed with the support of digital technology, such as Blockchain and Artificial Intelligence (AI), to improve the accuracy and security of financial data. Blockchain offers secure, transparent, and immutable transaction recording. While AI enables automation and data analysis to detect anomalies or fraud. With the application of this technology, the financial information system can further reduce the risk of human error, increase accountability, and support a more accurate and efficient data-based decision-making process (Handarini et al., 2025). With the increasing need for transparency and data security, financial information systems are starting to adopt technologies such as Blockchain and AI to increase efficiency and reduce the risk of fraud.

Digitalization of Financial Information Systems

Technological developments have driven the transformation of financial information systems from manual to digital recording. According to Fitari & Hartati (2022), digitalization of financial information systems changes financial recording from manual or printed formats to digital formats by utilizing technology and software. The main purpose of this digitalization is to increase the efficiency, accuracy, and accessibility of financial information. Digitalization of financial information systems provides various benefits, including:

1. Efficiency, speeding up the process of recording and reporting finances.
2. Accuracy, reducing the risk of human error in data input and processing.
3. Accessibility, allowing stakeholders to access data in real-time.

Although digitalization provides various benefits, its implementation still faces challenges, especially in terms of human resource readiness and management support (Arsyad et al., 2023). The implementation of digitalization of financial information systems faces several challenges (Santi et al., 2024):

1. Technical challenges

Infrastructure limitations, reliance on manual systems, and unstable internet connectivity can slow down the digitalization process, reducing the efficiency of financial management.

2. Limited human resources

The lack of trained workers and lack of training causes the use of digitalization of financial information systems to be suboptimal.

3. Policies and regulations

Complex bureaucracy and lack of flexible policies hinder the adoption of new technologies.

Discussion

Company Profile

PT ABC is an official distributor of glass products from PT XYZ, which distributes various products such as glasses, vases, jars, aquariums, and garden lights to the eastern part of Indonesia. With an extensive distribution network, the company serves various sectors, including hotels, restaurants, cafes, apartments, and households. PT ABC is committed to quality and delivery accuracy by implementing an integrated inventory management system to ensure stock availability and smooth distribution. To strengthen its position in the glass industry, the company continues to innovate in services and expand its market reach.

In addition to distributing high-quality glass products, PT ABC also serves custom requests according to customer needs. With the support of PT XYZ, the company is able to provide glass products with special designs, sizes, and colors. This process is carried out with high quality standards, combining craftsman skills and modern technology to produce exclusive products that suit customer preferences. This advantage gives PT ABC a stronger competitive edge in the glass industry and increases customer loyalty.

Challenges in Financial Management

Although PT ABC has implemented various strategies in distribution and custom services, the main challenge faced by the company is financial management which still relies on a manual system. With the increasing complexity of transactions and distribution volume, the manual system is no longer effective because it slows down the recording process, increases the risk of errors, and hinders fast and accurate decision making. In addition, the manual system causes a lack of transparency in financial recording, making it difficult for the company to conduct accurate financial analysis. The lack of data integration between various divisions makes it difficult to monitor cash flow, record receivables, and financial reporting in real time. The lack of an integrated system also has an impact on operational efficiency, especially in the billing process. Without an automated system, the company experiences delays in identifying stores that are past due or have a bad payment history. In addition, differences in report formats from each division hinder the synchronization of overall financial data. The payroll process which is still carried out manually increases the potential for calculation errors, which can impact compliance with tax regulations. Delays in the payroll process also have the potential to reduce employee satisfaction and affect their productivity.

Financial System Digitalization Solutions

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To overcome the various challenges that exist, PT ABC needs to implement an integrated digital-based financial information system. Some solutions that can be implemented include:

1. Automation of sales recording

By implementing a digital system, transaction recording can be done automatically, including issuing notes, updating stock, and preparing real-time sales reports. This allows companies to monitor monthly and annual turnover more accurately.

2. Digitizing the billing process

An integrated financial system allows companies to automatically identify customers who have passed their payment deadlines, thereby speeding up the billing process and reducing the risk of late payments. Automatic reminders can also be sent via email or WhatsApp to improve billing efficiency.

3. Implementation of a centralized payment system

By adopting digital payment methods such as bank transfers or giro, companies can increase financial transparency and reduce the potential for fraud in transactions. Integration with accounting systems also allows companies to directly match payments with invoices issued.

4. Payroll and tax automation

A digital system enables more accurate payroll calculations by automatically calculating taxes and making direct payments to employee accounts. In addition, tax system integration will ensure proper recording, reduce the risk of errors, and improve compliance with tax regulations.

5. Financial data security

The implementation of digital systems must be accompanied by strong security features, including data encryption, access restrictions based on authority, and regular data backups to prevent loss or leakage of information.

In implementing this solution, there are various systems or software that can be used to support its effectiveness. For example, PT ABC can consider using software such as Odoo, which provides automation features for recording sales, stock management, billing processes, and financial management in one platform. Thus, the company can have a more concrete picture of the implementation of this solution in its operations.

Challenges in Implementing Digitalization

Although digitalization offers many advantages, its implementation is not without challenges. One of the main obstacles is the readiness of human resources to adapt to the new system. Employees who are accustomed to using manual methods may have difficulty in understanding and operating digital systems. Therefore, regular training and socialization regarding the benefits of digitalization are essential. In addition, some customers may still be reluctant to use digital payment methods, so education and gradual adjustments need to be carried out. Companies must also consider the initial investment in software procurement, hardware, and system implementation costs, which may be an obstacle for companies with limited budgets. In addition to cost factors, the sustainability of the digitalization system must also be considered. Companies need to ensure adequate technical support and regular system updates so that digitalization runs optimally in the long term.

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CONCLUSION

Financial system digitization is a strategic step for PT ABC to improve operational efficiency, recording accuracy, and financial transparency. By automating sales, billing, payroll processes, and integrating tax systems, companies can optimize cash flow, accelerate decision-making, and minimize the risk of errors. However, successful implementation does not only depend on technology, but also on the readiness of human resources and management support. Therefore, employee training, customer education, and investment in the right system are key factors so that digitization truly has a positive and sustainable impact on the company. The implementation of financial digitization at PT ABC provides direct benefits, such as increased operational efficiency, financial data accuracy, and reduced risk of human error. With an integrated system, companies can increase transparency, accelerate data-based decision-making, and reduce long-term operational costs. In addition, digitization allows companies to be more flexible in dealing with regulatory changes and more adaptive to market dynamics.

In order for the digitalization of the financial system to run optimally, PT ABC needs to take strategic steps to maximize benefits and minimize risks. Here are some suggestions that can be applied:

1. Companies must provide regular training for employees so that they can operate the digital financial system optimally.
2. Given the risk of data leakage, companies must implement encryption, multi-factor authentication, and a strict security monitoring system.
3. Companies need to conduct regular audits and evaluations to ensure the system remains relevant to technological developments and business needs.
4. The digital financial system is connected to inventory management and customer relationship management (CRM) for more efficient operations.
5. Companies must continue to monitor and adjust existing digital systems with the latest tax policies and financial regulations to remain compliant with applicable laws.

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